

ISic1069

I.Sicily inscription 1069

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Mutyca

Place of origin (modern)

Modica

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Modica

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI140549

1. έκοιμή-

2. θη Κορνηλία

3. μηνι Όκτωβί-

4. ω ²⁶Οκτωβρίω²⁶, ότε από κα (λανδών) θ'

5. ήμέρα Διός.

6.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492696

EDCS 39102224

PHI 140549

Bibliography

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